

Code System

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Kappa

		Coder 1		
		1	0	
Coder 2	1	a = 32	b = 3	35
	0	c = 3	0	3
		35	3	38

$$P(\text{observed}) = P_o = a / (a + b + c) = 0.84$$

$$P(\text{chance}) = P_c = 1 / \text{Number of codes} = 1 / 11 = 0.09$$

$$\mathbf{Kappa = (P_o - P_c) / (1 - P_c) = 0.83}$$

If there is an unequal number of codes per segment or if only one code is to be evaluated:

$$P(\text{chance}) = P_c = \text{Number of codes} / (\text{Number of codes} + 1)^2 = 0.08$$

$$\mathbf{Kappa = (P_o - P_c) / (1 - P_c) = 0.83}$$

Code System

Code System	Memo	Frequency
Code System		496
1. Contextual Shifts	<p>Definition: This category captures interview content where negotiation is framed as being shaped by broader external developments. These can be geopolitical (wars, power relations), societal (migration, polarization), or ecological (climate change). The focus is on drivers and constraints that set the stage for negotiations, not on the negotiations themselves.</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees link negotiation dynamics to external contexts or structural shifts. Then assign to the relevant subcode (1.1 Geopolitical, 1.2 Social, 1.3 Climate).</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage is about individual negotiation cases (→ 3 Challenging Experiences), about cultural styles (→ 2), or about civil society/academia directly (→ 4).</p>	0
1.1. Geopolitical	<p>Definition: This code captures passages where interviewees describe how current interstate politics, wars, authoritarian regimes, or violations of international law shape negotiations. It includes direct references to armed conflict, sanctions, or shifts in international norms that affect negotiation opportunities or constraints. The information extracted here helps reconstruct how practitioners perceive the broader geopolitical environment of their work.</p> <p>Example Quote: “We now see obvious violations of international, fundamental principles of international law by Russia and others.” (Kristoffer Lidén)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees explicitly or implicitly connect negotiation dynamics (opportunities, barriers, legitimacy, urgency) to current international politics or geopolitical events based on the actions of governments or governing bodies.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The focus is on domestic/social trends like migration or populism (→ 1.2 Social). The speaker discusses bureaucratic or institutional slowness within organizations (→ 3.2 What Made It Hard). The driver is climate/environment (→ 1.3 Climate).</p>	34
1.2. Social	<p>Definition: This code covers passages where interviewees describe how societal changes — such as migration flows, polarization, the rise of populism, or fragmentation of civic trust — affect negotiations. It includes both negative effects (e.g., erosion of consensus, polarization) and positive dynamics (e.g., grassroots mobilization). The extracted information documents how societal currents are seen as reshaping negotiation contexts.</p> <p>Example Quote: “The ongoing migration crisis in Europe and the full-scale invasion of the war in Ukraine have really reshaped the humanitarian negotiation space.” (Stéphanie Ferland)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when the negotiation environment is linked to</p>	26

	<p>broader societal dynamics or transformations.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: Civil society is described as direct negotiation actors (→ 4.2 Civil Society & Negotiation). Geopolitical/military conflicts are the driver (→ 1.1 Geopolitical).</p>	
1.3. Climate	<p>Definition: This code captures mentions of climate change and environmental factors as negotiation drivers, agenda items, or obstacles. It highlights how practitioners see ecological issues not only as background conditions but as active topics structuring negotiation spaces. The extracted information shows how environmental concerns are integrated into negotiation practice.</p> <p>Example Quote: “Climate change requires globally coordinated leadership to negotiate effective solutions.” (Anne-Marie Goetz)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply only when the physical environmental parts of climate change, sustainability, or ecological consequences are explicitly tied to negotiation processes.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage only describes humanitarian access problems without linking them to climate/environment. The dominant driver is geopolitical (→ 1.1).</p>	9
2. Regional and Cultural Styles	<p>Definition: This category captures interview content where negotiation is described in terms of cultural or regional style differences. The focus is on how groups of actors are perceived to negotiate, either within Europe or outside. It emphasizes generalized patterns, norms, and expectations rather than single cases.</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees generalize about the way Europeans (→ 2.1) or non-Europeans (→ 2.2) negotiate.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage narrates a single difficult negotiation case (→ 3), or describes general social/geopolitical context (→ 1).</p>	0
2.1. European	<p>Definition: This code captures generalizations about negotiation styles perceived as “European,” such as norm-driven, ethics-oriented, consensus-seeking, or process-heavy approaches. It reflects how practitioners characterize European identity in negotiation practice. The extracted information provides material for reconstructing perceived regional negotiation cultures.</p> <p>Example Quote: “Europeans still insist on normative frameworks, even if it makes things harder.” (Kristoffer Lidén)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when Europe or Europeans are described collectively as negotiating in a distinct manner.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The style is attributed to non-European contexts (→ 2.2). The segment narrates a specific case rather than general style (→ 3.1).</p>	70

2.2. Non-European	<p>Definition: This code captures perceptions of negotiation practices outside Europe, such as patience, informal rituals, or culturally specific approaches. It highlights comparative views between European and non-European styles. The extracted information provides data on how practitioners interpret intercultural differences.</p> <p>Example Quote: “In China, you might drink tea for weeks before talking politics.” (Rational Games)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees describe cultural or regional negotiation practices beyond Europe.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The story is mainly about a difficult case (→ 3). The passage is about general social changes (→ 1.2).</p>	16
3. Challenging Experiences (Individual)	<p>Definition: This category captures interview content where negotiation is described as difficult or demanding. It includes full case narratives, perceived obstacles, and reflections on outcome drivers. The emphasis is on what practitioners experience as hard in practice, whether in specific episodes or in general obstacles/outcomes.</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees talk about the difficulty of negotiation. Then assign to subcodes: 3.1 Case Narratives, 3.2 Obstacles, or 3.3 Outcome Drivers. Use the rule that if a full story is told, code under 3.1. If not, choose between 3.2 and 3.3.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage is only about cultural/regional negotiation style (→ 2) or about macro-level shifts (→ 1).</p>	2
3.1. Case Description	<p>Definition: This code captures passages where interviewees narrate specific negotiation episodes they consider especially difficult. It involves contextual detail (who, where, what issue) and frames the episode as a “challenge.” The extracted information provides concrete cases illustrating perceived difficulty.</p> <p>Example Quote: “Negotiating the UN Security Council Resolution 1820 on sexual violence in warfare was exhausting—it took years and massive coalition building.” (Anne-Marie Goetz)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when the speaker gives a full case account, usually including setting, actors, conflict, and difficulty.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: Only barriers are listed without storytelling (→ 3.2). Only outcome factors are highlighted (→ 3.3).</p>	22
3.1.1. Challenges	<p>Definition: This code captures mentions of obstacles, such as institutional inertia, cultural barriers, or lack of trust, that made negotiations difficult. The extracted information provides insight into perceived barriers.</p> <p>Example Quote: “The EU's decision-making process is too slow—</p>	51

	<p>everyone has different interests.” (Alina Vlasenko)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees explain difficulties or barriers without narrating a full episode. It can be double coded with 3.1. to distinguish challenging factors of the case description.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The emphasis is on success/failure determinants (→ 3.3).</p>	
3.1.2. Outcome Determinants	<p>Definition: This code captures mentions of causal factors that shaped negotiation results (success, failure, or breakthrough). It includes preparation, alliances, or framing choices. The extracted information highlights practitioners’ understanding of negotiation outcomes.</p> <p>Example Quote: “We worked with military advisors and even spouses of ambassadors to build unusual alliances for that resolution.” (Anne-Marie Goetz)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when speakers explicitly connect outcome to specific factors or mechanisms. It can be double coded with 3.1. to specify the outcome of the case description.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The segment focuses on challenges without outcome reflections (→ 3.2).</p>	16
4. Research, Practice and Civil Society	<p>Definition: This category captures interview content where negotiation is discussed in relation to knowledge and actor gaps: between researchers and practitioners, between institutions and civil society, or where bridging strategies are proposed. The focus is on connections and disconnections between negotiation and surrounding knowledge/public spheres.</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees talk about academia, public perception, or civil society in relation to negotiations. Then assign to subcodes: 4.1 Research–Practice Gap, 4.2 Civil Society & Negotiation, or 4.3 Bridge Strategies.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage is about training methods for negotiators (→ 5), or general contextual shifts like migration or war (→ 1).</p>	0
4.1. Research / Practice Gap	<p>Definition: This code captures perceptions of academic theories as disconnected from negotiation practice. It highlights interviewees’ complaints about abstraction or lack of practical relevance. The extracted information documents how practitioners see the knowledge divide.</p> <p>Example Quote: “Academia doesn’t offer a language for the moral dilemmas mediators face.” (Kristoffer Lidén)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees criticize academic negotiation research as not useful or disconnected.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage instead proposes a bridging activity (→ 4.3).</p>	39

<p>4.2. Civil Society & Negotiation</p>	<p>Definition: This code captures mentions of civil society (NGOs, grassroots, communities, media) as actors in negotiations. It includes roles such as being influential, excluded, or misunderstood. The extracted information shows how practitioners see civil society in negotiation processes.</p> <p>Example Quote: “Civil society uniting during the war was one of the most powerful negotiation forces in Ukraine.” (Alina Vlasenko)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when civil society is presented as a negotiation actor with influence (positive or negative).</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage describes general social change without actorhood (→ 1.2).</p>	<p>25</p>
<p>4.3. Bridging Strategies</p>	<p>Definition: This code captures suggestions for connecting research, practice, and civil society, such as podcasts, films, or storytelling. It highlights interviewees’ ideas for communication and translation across spheres. The extracted information documents proposed solutions for knowledge gaps.</p> <p>Example Quote: “We created a podcast to make negotiation ideas more accessible.” (Rational Games)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees propose or describe concrete bridging tools or strategies.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage is about training methods for negotiators (→ 5.3).</p>	<p>30</p>
<p>5. Skills and Learning</p>	<p>Definition: This category captures interview content about what skills negotiators need and how they are developed. It includes general skill expectations, lived demonstrations of skill in practice, and teaching methods. The focus is on competencies, behaviors, and pedagogy.</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees mention skills, behaviors, or methods of learning. Then assign to subcodes: 5.1 Essential Skills, 5.2 Skills Demonstrated, or 5.3 Teaching Methods.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage is about civil society outreach (→ 4.3) or contextual drivers like war/politics (→ 1).</p>	<p>0</p>
<p>5.1. Essential Skills</p>	<p>Definition: This code captures skills or qualities described as universally important for negotiators (e.g., humility, empathy, listening, preparation). The extracted information shows normative expectations of good negotiation practice.</p> <p>Example Quote: “Humility is the root of everything—without it, you can’t listen or learn.” (Valérie Rosoux)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees make general statements about necessary skills, often using modal verbs (“must, should,</p>	<p>27</p>

	<p>need to”).</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The skill is illustrated via a specific anecdote (→ 5.2). The subject is how to teach these essential skills (→ 5.3).</p>	
5.2. Skills Demonstrated	<p>Definition: This code captures anecdotal accounts where interviewees describe applying skills in practice. It provides examples of how skills are enacted in real situations.</p> <p>Example Quote: “In Brussels, I had to shift from climate policy to human tragedy to make people listen.” (Alina Vlasenko)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when the segment describes concrete moments where skills were demonstrated.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The segment is abstract skill talk (→ 5.1) or pedagogy (→ 5.3).</p>	0
5.3. Teaching Methods	<p>Definition: This code captures strategies and tools for teaching or learning negotiation (e.g., simulations, role-plays, reflective spaces). The extracted information shows pedagogical approaches.</p> <p>Example Quote: “We do simulations and theatre games—people learn better when they play.” (Rational Games)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when the focus is on how negotiation skills are taught, practiced, or learned.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The segment is about public outreach (→ 4.3).</p>	22
5.4. Lessons Learned	<p>Definition: Passages where interviewees describe situations from which they gained an insight, realization, or changed perspective. This can include mistakes, turning points, or takeaways from experience.</p> <p>Example Quote: “At first I followed the company’s strict strategy, and I almost blew up the negotiation. That’s when I learned how important it is to adapt and be transparent.” (Kalafati)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when the focus is on the learning outcome of an experience (e.g., “I learned that...” / “This taught me...”).</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The segment describes a skill in action without reflection (→ 5.2). The segment is about formal teaching/training settings (→ 5.3).</p>	18
5.1. Essential Skills and Requirements	<p>Definition: This code captures skills or qualities described as universally important for negotiators (e.g., humility, empathy, listening, preparation). The extracted information shows normative expectations of good negotiation practice.</p> <p>Example Quote: “Humility is the root of everything—without it, you</p>	47

	<p>can't listen or learn." (Valérie Rosoux)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees make general statements about necessary skills, often using modal verbs ("must, should, need to").</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The skill is illustrated via a specific anecdote (→ 5.2). The subject is how to teach these essential skills (→ 5.3).</p> <p>05/01/26 20:03 - fil Merged with code 5. Skills and Learning > 5.1. Essential Skills</p> <p>5.1. Essential Skills Created: fred, 29/09/25 03:15 Modified: fred, 29/09/25 14:33</p> <p>Definition: This code captures skills or qualities described as universally important for negotiators (e.g., humility, empathy, listening, preparation). The extracted information shows normative expectations of good negotiation practice.</p> <p>Example Quote: "Humility is the root of everything—without it, you can't listen or learn." (Valérie Rosoux)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees make general statements about necessary skills, often using modal verbs ("must, should, need to").</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The skill is illustrated via a specific anecdote (→ 5.2).</p>	
<p>6. Future Directions</p>	<p>Definition: This category captures interview content that looks forward to the future of negotiations. It includes open research questions, predicted risks/challenges, and reflections on changing narratives. The focus is on forward-looking perspectives.</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees explicitly talk about future needs, risks, or narratives. Then assign to subcodes: 6.1 Questions for Research, 6.2 Anticipated Challenges, 6.3 Shifting Narratives.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage only reflects on current skills (→ 5) or contextual shifts already happening (→ 1).</p>	<p>0</p>
<p>6.1. Research Questions</p>	<p>Definition: This code captures open research or practice questions that interviewees say should be addressed in the future. It highlights perceived gaps in knowledge or practice.</p> <p>Example Quote: "We need to study how to teach people to let go of needing to win." (Rational Games)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when interviewees explicitly phrase a question or knowledge gap.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The segment predicts risks without framing them as research</p>	<p>28</p>

	questions (→ 6.2).	
6.2. Anticipated Challenges	<p>Definition: This code captures predictions of risks, crises, or threats for future negotiations (e.g., AI, fragmentation, mistrust). It highlights interviewees' outlook on negotiation challenges.</p> <p>Example Quote: "Negotiators without AI will be replaced. It's not a question of if, but when." (Claude Bruderlein)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when the speaker forecasts obstacles for future practice.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The passage is framed as a research question (→ 6.1).</p>	13
6.3. Shifting Narratives	<p>Definition: This code captures reflections on dominant or changing storylines in negotiation discourse (e.g., return to transactionalism, loss of hope). It documents how interviewees frame negotiation as a discourse.</p> <p>Example Quote: "There's a return to transactional, 'let's make a deal' thinking—and it's dangerous." (Valérie Rosoux)</p> <p>Coding Rule: Apply when speakers highlight how negotiations are talked about, interpreted, or valued.</p> <p>Do Not Code If: The segment is about regional cultural style (→ 2).</p>	1